

Students' Views: International Relations Journal

Volume 1, 2025/2026

FACULTAD DE COMERCIO Y
RELACIONES LABORALES

Universidad de Valladolid

Autores

Los artículos han sido elaborados por los alumnos de la asignatura **Lengua Extranjera para las Relaciones Internacionales (Inglés)** de la Facultad de Comercio y Relaciones Laborales de la Universidad de Valladolid como parte de su evaluación durante el curso 2025/2026.

Authors

*The articles published in this issue have been authored by students taking the course **Lengua Extranjera para las Relaciones Internacionales (Inglés)** at the Faculty of Commerce and Labour Relations of the University of Valladolid (Spain). They were produced as part of the students' assessment for the 2025/2026 academic year.*

Revisores

A través del proyecto e-tandem virtual TAPP (Transatlantic and Pacific Project) los estudiantes han colaborado con los alumnos de la asignatura **TCOM 6318 - Stylistics and Editing** – University of Houston-Downtown (EE. UU.), quienes han actuado como correctores y revisores.

Reviewers

*As part of the virtual e-tandem TAPP (Transatlantic and Pacific Project), the students collaborated with students taking **TCOM 6318 – Stylistics and Editing** at the University of Houston-Downtown (USA), who served as peer editors and reviewers.*

Protección de datos

La publicación de esta revista cumple con la legislación en materia de protección de datos, habiéndose recabado el permiso de todos los autores para hacer público su trabajo.

Data protection

The publication of this journal complies with data protection regulations, and the consent of all authors has been obtained for the public dissemination of their work.

Exención de responsabilidad

El Equipo editorial y la Institución no se hacen responsables de los puntos de vista y opiniones expresadas por los autores, ni del contenido de los artículos publicados en la revista.

Disclaimer

The Editorial Team and the Institution are not responsible for the views and opinions expressed by the authors, nor for the content of the articles published in the journal.

Editor: Leticia Moreno-Pérez, PhD (UVa)

Valladolid, junio de 2026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20625692

TABLE OF CONTENTS

The Rise of Polarisation Worldwide

África Reguera Zapico, Irene Rodríguez Gómez 4

How a President's Statement Could Lead to a Bilateral Crisis

Maidor González de Uriarte, Andrea Fernández Puente..... 9

The Battle for Global Power: America and China's New Cold War

Claudia Moya, Ángela Macías 12

The Multidimensional Impact of European Union Migration Policy on Mediterranean Countries

Ayşe Yayla, Rabia Günder 19

The Danish American Diplomatic Dispute over Greenland

Daniel Seweryn, Paula de la Rosa Gómez 23

AI and AI-Based Disinformation and Its Impact on International Politics

Emirhan Demirci, Emirhan Can Akkoyun 26

Türkiye's Political Stance in the Russia-Ukraine War

Prince Mboungou, Esmannur Sultan Toklucu 29

Can a Neutral Language Save International Law?

Eva Rodríguez Díez 33

Can We Stay Human in a World of War?

Iván Labarta Jaria 40

The 2026 American-Israeli Attack on Iran

Pedro Manuel Fanego Díaz 44

The Rise of Polarisation Worldwide

África Reguera Zapico

Irene Rodríguez Gómez

In recent days we all are always listening and using the word “polarisation”, but do we really know its meaning? It has different interpretations, here are some of its definitions:

In politics, an increasingly stark and antagonistic division between political parties, groups, or viewpoints, and the accompanying decline of moderate or centrist positions that normally mediate those differences. (Oxford University Press, n.d.); the act of dividing something, especially something that contains different people or opinions, into two completely opposing groups. (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d.); the splitting of society into opposing groups and deepening ideological, political, social and emotional confrontations (Zamfir, 2025).

The key words to understand polarisation are “division”, “opinion” and “society”.

Some people wrongly assume that polarisation is a new phenomenon of our century. It has existed for a long period of time; there have always been opposite points of view and people that take advantage of it. A great example of it is the worldwide division during the World Wars and the Cold War. Currently, we are experiencing a raising of the polarisation worldwide, this paper discusses its causes and provides examples.

As it has been said, present-day society around the world is divided, but at the same time, one of the most influential factors in global polarisation is globalisation. At first sight, this may seem contradictory because this means that all the world is connected. So how can a world that is connected be divided at the same time? Currently, one thing that happens in one part of the world influences the rest of the world. This means that whether society is divided it does not only happen in a specific country or region, but also all over the world.

Along with this, the economic and political instability and uncertainty worldwide make individuals to feel the need to belong to groups with the same values and political opinions. This gives them a feeling of certainty in finding a solution to the problems that exist and the feeling of not being alone. Aware of this societal need, different influential actors such as politicians and the media take advantage of it by spreading fake news and disinformation to create confrontation among the population. As a result, two opposite points of view emerge, which makes the population of one part to be mistrustful with the other part. Once society is divided, it is easier to control. This means that those that want power and do not care about peace and democracy, look for polarisation.

A clear manifestation of international polarisation are the tensions between Western democracies and authoritarian powers such as China and Russia. Competition in areas such as trade, security and technology are increasing. These divisions have caused more fragmentation in the international order and have made cooperation on global challenges more difficult.

The competition over technological leadership essentially in areas such as artificial intelligence, telecommunications, and digital infrastructure has become a central element of this polarisation. Countries are increasingly pressured to align themselves with one of these competing spheres of influence, which make the formation of geopolitical blocs stronger.

Moreover, security challenges have also contributed to this issue. Military alliances, strategic partnerships, and regional conflicts have deepened distrust between different powers, making diplomatic cooperation more complex. In this context, international organisations often struggle to maintain consensus among their members, as states prioritise their strategic interests and alliances.

People are accustomed to the polarisation previously mentioned, but there is another one that is very present, but is not recognised. It has a real impact on the world and international relations. This hidden type is North-South polarisation in the world.

The differences between the North and South are not only for economic reasons and differences, but mainly because of the unequal distribution of power in the international system and the perception of belonging to certain blocs. The world is divided into two parts, North that usually refers to industrialized and wealthy countries

that have very high levels of development; while the South refers to developing or less industrialized countries (Josefina del Prado, 1998).

However, this division goes beyond income or economic indicators. There are more reasons. One of those is very remarkable because the countries of the North part have greater influence in major international institutions such as the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank, which allows it to influence international economic and political rules. In contrast, the South, despite representing more than three quarters of the world's population, produces a very much smaller proportion of global wealth and lacks a strong common position because of its internal diversity. Furthermore, this division does not only exist between states but also within them, where elites are often more connected to Northern interests than to the needs of their own societies.

For decades, specifically after decolonisation and the end of the Cold War, this difference has not disappeared. Instead, it has evolved in many ways, becoming much severe. Although some emerging economies have entered a "grey zone" due to their economic growth, belonging to the North still depends mainly on the real power, which is the capacity to exercise power, including influencing the international order. This shows that the North-South divide is based more on structures of dominance and power than on simple differences in levels of development.

In conclusion, polarisation is not a new phenomenon as it has existed throughout history. However, its scale and intensity in the contemporary world make it one of the most significant challenges for global society. It appears due to the economic, political and military uncertainty worldwide. Rather than a unified system based on broad international cooperation, the world appears to be moving toward a scenario in which geopolitical rivalry and ideological differences increasingly shape international relations.

With the latest current global events, if states and international actors' actions remain unchanged, polarisation will undoubtedly be reinforced. For this reason, understanding the mechanisms that drive polarisation is essential for building more stable and cooperative international relations.

References

- ArXiv. (2023). [Preprint article]. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.18535>
- Atlantic Council. (2023, February 2). *Implementing NATO's strategic concept on China*. <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/in-depth-research-reports/report/implementing-natos-strategic-concept-on-china/>
- Brookings Institution. (n.d.). *U.S. vs. China*. <https://www.brookings.edu/>
- Cambridge University Press. (n.d.). *Polarization*. In *Cambridge Dictionary*. Retrieved March 17, 2026, from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/polarization>
- Council on Foreign Relations. (2022, September 14). *Renewing America series: The growing divide—Polarization in the United States* [Event]. <https://www.cfr.org/event/renewing-america-series-growing-divide-polarization-united-states>
- Duke University. (n.d.). *How did political polarization begin and where does it end?* <https://impact.duke.edu/story/how-did-political-polarization-begin-and-where-does-it-end>
- European Commission. (n.d.). *Spotlight on polarisation*. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/radicalisation-awareness-network-ran/ran-media/ran-spotlight/spotlight-polarisation_en
- European Political Science Review. (n.d.). *Does polarization increase participation? A systematic literature review and meta-analysis*.
- European Union. (2023). *The surprising reason why society is so divided*. <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/462112-the-surprising-reason-why-society-is-so-divided>
- Insurance Business Magazine. (2025). *Global stability enters "grey zone" era as businesses face new geopolitical risks*. <https://www.insurancebusinessmag.com/asia/news/breaking-news/report-global->

[stability-enters-greystone-era-as-businesses-face-new-class-of-geopolitical-risk-566653.aspx](#)

National Center for Biotechnology Information. (2024). *[Article]*.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC12595431/>

Oxford University Press. (n.d.). *Oxford Reference*. Retrieved March 17, 2026,
from
<https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/oi/authority.20111121090324389>

Prado, J. del. (1998). *[Article PDF]*. Dialnet.
<https://dialnet.unirioja.es/descarga/articulo/6302256.pdf>

Schwartz, M. (2021, October 14). *Why we're so polarized*. Center for Strategic and International Studies. <https://www.csis.org/podcasts/truth-matter/why-were-so-polarized>

University of Gadjah Mada. (2023). *The world faces growing polarization*.
<https://ugm.ac.id/en/news/the-world-faces-growing-polarization/>

Zamfir, I. (2025). *Understanding political polarisation*. European Parliament.
<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/299492/Understanding-political-polarisation.pdf>

How a President's Statement Could Lead to a Bilateral Crisis

Maidor González de Uriarte

Andrea Fernández Puente

Can a single sentence from a country's president unravel over fifty years of delicate diplomatic peace? In the 1972 Japan-China Joint Communiqué, Japan established a diplomatic baseline by stating it fully understands and respects that Taiwan is part of the People's Republic of China. What's more, Japan affirmed in the treaty that they will not interfere if China starts a unification by force, prioritizing their society's peace and national security. However, recent rhetoric has dramatically called into question this status quo. Japan's Prime Minister, Takaichi, recently declared that Japan would intervene if China used force to integrate Taiwan, arguing such a scenario would create a serious security threat for Japan. The status of this relationship is currently hanging by a thread, not only heightening the bilateral crisis between both countries but foretelling a disturbance in global stability. Both perspective quarrels demonstrate how a single statement from a head of government can lead to the disregard of historical diplomatic agreements.

Taking into account Beijing's point of view, any type of rhetorical shift from Japan regarding Taiwan would be a direct violation in accordance with the base in diplomacy from 1972 that was established in the Joint Communiqué. However, China's principle of "One China" is the one thing they are not flexible about when it comes to funding bilateral relations. They discuss that the latest comments that the Prime Minister made are an illegal intervention in internal affairs, and a provocation that ignores many diplomatic agreements from many decades ago. Moreover, these events are more than just mere speaking, they are also a strategic menace to the national sovereignty of China. Therefore, the definition of security concerns for Japan is not the same for China; since China understands it as a strategic disloyalty of the institutional consensus after the war.

In stark contrast, Tokyo maintains that today's global environment is on a knife-edge, hence they frame it as a matter of fundamental national survival. Similarly to the 1950s Taiwan Straits Crisis initiated, Japan fears being inevitably dragged into a regional war. Should an armed conflict arise, Tokyo's longstanding alliance with the United States and the heavy presence of American military bases on Japanese territory

would make neutrality nearly impossible. Furthermore, the justification for a conflict would just debilitate vital maritime supply chains. Given Japan's reliance on seaborne trade and their vast influence in worldwide economy, a blockade in mentioned Strait would lead to severe economic circumstances. As a result, Japanese administration's statement serves as a strategic wake-up call to rally the Japanese masses, identified as essentially neutral.

Ultimately, when two opposing narratives clash, the already fragile stability of the time transforms into a deep bilateral crisis that in the long run is such a bigger conflict to solve. When a contradiction arises between powerful leaders and historical agreements, it creates a feeling of mistrust that endangers the cooperation of the rest of the parts. This conflict about "words" is more than a superficial and conversation topic, since it leads directly to the triggering of a military budget arise and the reinforcement of the foreign policies from both narratives. All in all, the rhetoric in politics acts like a catalyst since it creates and intensifies the uncertainty and tension in the relations of Japan and China.

Overall, the complex world of diplomacy is biased, which can be proved by observing acts over words. China's response over Japan's Prime Minister declaration led to a different conversation on how conflicts arise, highlighting that the delicate diplomatic baseline of the 1972 Joint Communiqué was fractured. While one defends its sovereignty and the other backs up on their matter of national survival, it is clear that the 20th and 21st centuries along with the influence of globalization, actual diplomatic issues cannot be dismissed as superficial. On the whole, only one sentence from a powerful person can trigger off many decades of conflict and compromise the peace of two countries very deeply. Regarding the first question mentioned, indeed, a sentence from a president can unravel more than fifty years of fragile peace in diplomacy. Words are as impactful as acts in the globalized international world.

References

The Japan-China joint communique and the question of Taiwan. (2025, diciembre). *The Diplomat*. <https://thediplomat.com/2025/12/the-japan-china-joint-communiqué-and-the-question-of-taiwan/>

The breakdown in Japan-China relations. (s.f.). *Politics Today*.
<https://politicstoday.org/the-breakdown-in-japan-china-relations/>

Manohar Parrikar Institute for Defence Studies and Analyses. (2025, noviembre). *Japan digest: November 2025*. <https://www.idsa.in/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Japan-Digest-November-2025.pdf>

Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan. (1972). *Joint communique of the Government of Japan and the Government of the People's Republic of China*.
<https://www.mofa.go.jp/region/asia-paci/china/joint72.html>

Office of the Historian. (s.f.). *The Taiwan Straits crises: 1954–55 and 1958*.
United States Department of State. <https://history.state.gov/milestones/1953-1960/taiwan-strait-crises>

The Battle for Global Power: America and China's New Cold War

Claudia Moya
Ángela Macías

Almost 36 years ago, the fall of the Berlin Wall seemed to mark the end of the great-power ideological rivalry. Yet, almost three decades later, a new strategic competition is reshaping global politics. This confrontation reflects the struggle between Washington and Moscow, as well as the growing distrust and economic tensions. This suggests that a new era of rivalry may already be underway.

To better understand whether current tensions can truly constitute a new cold war, it is essential that we compare the characteristics of both the new and old conflict.

- Proxy wars were founded mainly in the U.S. side from Ukraine, in the Russian side from, Iran and with a new third actor, China, and the Taiwan and economic trade wars.
- They switched from military power to economic power and technology.
- Espionage is still a main issue in all the countries involved in the power struggle. This can be seen in new espionage efforts, such as the CIA new recruitment videos in mandarin¹. This can also be reflected in economic and military espionage², especially with new economic areas, such as microchips in countries like Taiwan and cyberattacks.³
- What was known as the “space race” is now known as a technological race, mainly between US and China. It is known to be characterized by the rise of technological intelligence such as AI and components such as microchips.
- One of the main changes is the military alliance. Back in the Cold War era, the two sides were the Soviets, with the Warsaw pact, and the NATO side, with almost all occidental superpowers such as the EU. Right now, NATO is the only

¹ De la Cal, L., & De la Cal, L. (2026b, 19th january). USA and China intensify their spy war: CIA launches recruitment videos in Mandarin. *El Mundo América*.

² *Allegations of espionage, theft add fuel to the fire in US-China chip war.*

³ Da Costa, C. (2026b, 20th february). *Chinese Hackers Bypassed a U.S. Government VPN, Raising New Cybersecurity Concerns*. Yahoo News.

alliance one still standing, and China and Russia have their own independent alliances.

- Propaganda was another one of the main elements in the cold war, or in conflicts in general, and this has not changed in the current world. For example, Russia has spent more than 300 million since 2014 to influence politics outside of their country⁴.

China's Side

If one word could describe China's side of the cold war, it would be assertiveness. They have shown an aggressive reaction where their competences have been slightly threatened by the USA's economic or military power. This can be translated as one of the biggest geopolitical issues currently: Taiwan has been a silent battlefield in the topics of, especially, microchips, given that approximately 90% percent of the more advanced, more used logic chips are made exclusively in Taiwan⁵. China has already claimed this territory as theirs, and while the official Taiwanese government has defended continuously its independence.

This issue has been extrapolated to two different topics outside of the Taiwan conflict: rare earth weaponization and nuclear expansion. In October of last year, Beijing announced restrictions on rare earth exports, which are key raw materials in the manufacturing of both defense products, such as F-35 jets, and electronics (from main brands such as Apple).

USA's Side

The new cold war is characterized by geopolitical, economic and technological competition rather than a military conflict as trying to compete over the global leadership. One reason could be that China is aiming to displace the United States as the world's power; they are a technology and security rivalry.

For decades the U.S. desired engagement by integrating China into the global economy. However, tensions increased again starting in 2018 when the U.S. began a

⁴ TheGuardian (2022b, september 13). *Russia has spent \$300m since 2014 to influence foreign officials, US says*. The Guardian.

⁵ Global Taiwan Institute. (2025b, march 5). *Taiwan's Shortage of Chipmakers: A Major Threat to the Industry's Long-term Growth*.

trade war. They argued that economic openness had strengthened China without making its political system more liberal⁶.

Today the rivalry continues through economic and technological competition, especially over advanced chips and AI as mentioned before⁷. Military and political tensions around Taiwan and other countries involved in the “cold war” known as proxy wars are also part of the recent events. Trump's new era or 2.0 era have kept stability although differences between ideologies and forms of action still exist.⁸

Are countries being forced to “choose sides” again, like during the Cold War?

No, countries are not being forced to choose sides. This has been the norm for every bilateral conflict, including the last cold war, but it has proven to not be true with this new conflict, dividing countries into two categories.

In the first stance lie countries like Brazil or India, who are balancing their relationships in order to avoid a total allegiance to the US or China-Russia led bloc. For example, in the case of India this has been shown by joining organizations like the BRICS, where China is a member, while also maintaining US relationships by being part of The Quadrilateral Security Dialogue, with Japan and Australia.

In the second stance, however, we can find countries who have been proven to not react to either side or maintain relationships with both whiles being politically independent. The main example of neutrality in this case is the country-state of Singapore, with long standing Chinese economic relationships. Despite this, Singapore leaders have already clarified they won't act based on blind neutrality, but on international law principles should conflict arise.

So, if they are countries who either do not pick sides or side with both countries, why is it better to partake in proxy conflicts and not solve them directly? Well, the answer is pretty simple. Proxy wars do not require countries to involve themselves directly in the conflict, however close indirect they may be.

⁶ Asia for Educators, Columbia University. *Asia for Educators* | Columbia University.

⁷ EPOCH INVESTMENT PARTNERS. The U.S.- China Trade War: What to expect in 2026

⁸ U.S. NAVAL INSTITUTE. The War of 2026: Phase III Scenario

First, proxy conflicts entail that relationships between both countries might not be as damaged as they would if it was a formal conflict; The economic ties economic ties do not need to be severed straight away, making them economically profitable.

Second, superpowers use proxy wars to shift balance of power in a determined area, secure vital resources (such as oil in conflicts in the Middle East) .And install favorable governments in strategic regions, usually because of economic interests.

Is the real battlefield of the new Cold War technology and trade rather than direct military conflict?

Unlike the 20th century, U.S. and the Soviet Union rivalry, which was defined by ideological blocks and direct nuclear dissuasion. The current geopolitical competition is based on rather trade than military conflict. We could say it's a "Digital Cold War" as Harvard Business Review says.⁹ While proxy conflicts and security tensions are still happening, the main struggle is the race to technological standards and economic rules that will define global power in the 21st century, and what country is the world's leader.

Why is China centering itself around the economic topic and not the military one? Why is the U.S or Russia not sharing those views?

China focuses more on economic development rather than military confrontation, because of its long-term strategy for gaining global power. Also, China believes the world has moved into economic growth and development rather than a direct military conflict.

Because of this, China prioritizes reform, opening its economy, and building global economic partnerships. By becoming a major economic power and creating initiatives like international partnerships and trade networks, China can increase its influence in global affairs without direct military conflict. Military confrontation with major powers could damage economic development. Therefore, China prefers to stay out of them without leaving the military preparation out.

⁹ Taneja, H., & Zakaria, F. (2023, 6 september). *AI and the New Digital Cold War*. Harvard Business Review.

In the other hands, United States or Russia do not fully share this view, United States aims to maintain global leadership and a unipolar world order, which requires strong military power and alliances. The U.S. sees China as a strategic competitor with economic, political, and military capabilities, so it emphasizes technological superiority. Countries like the U.S. and Russia traditionally rely on military strength and alliances to protect their influence on global politics. While China stresses economic development, the U.S. and Russia often view global competition more through security and military rivalry, especially in some areas like nuclear weapons and alliances.¹⁰

Is it really a “cold war”, or can it escalate to a real, global military conflict?

Whether the current rivalry is truly a “new Cold War” or could escalate into a global military conflict remains an open and complex question. On one hand, many characteristics resemble the Cold War of the 20th century.

However, today’s competition is not only military or ideological but also strongly centered on economic power and technological leadership. The struggle over microchips, artificial intelligence, and rare earth materials shows it. But if economic and technological rivalry defines power today, does that make the conflict less dangerous or different? At the same time, several factors reduce the likelihood of a direct global war.

The deep economic interdependence between countries such as the United States and China means that a full-scale conflict would cause massive global economic disruption. For this reason, proxy wars, cyberattacks, and diplomatic pressure have become the preferred ways to compete while avoiding escalation. Ultimately, the current situation may be best understood not as a simple repetition of the Cold War, but as a new form of rivalry in a multipolar and globalized world.

This creates a more complex and unpredictable international system, where countries are not always forced to choose sides but instead try to balance their interests between different powers. Therefore, the central question remains unresolved: will this competition remain “cold,” or could it eventually turn “hot”? Will technological and economic rivalry prevent war? The answer may depend on the actions of the major

¹⁰ Davis, D. (2024, 15 october). *Responsibly competing with China*. Defense Priorities.

powers, but also on how the international community takes on the competition, diplomacy, and cooperation.

References

De la Cal, L. (2026, 19 jan). USA and China intensify their spy war: CIA launches recruitment videos in Mandarin. *ELMUNDOAMERICA*. <https://www.mundoamerica.com/news/2026/01/19/696e1d0ffdddf4f378b457d.html>

Davis, D. (2024, 15 oct). *Responsibly competing with China*. Defense Priorities. <https://www.defensepriorities.org/explainers/responsibly-competing-withchina/#:~:text=Key%20points,international%20institutions%20to%20their%20advantage>

Da Costa, C. (2026b, feb 20). Chinese Hackers Bypassed a U.S. Government VPN, Raising New Cybersecurity Concerns. *Yahoo News*. https://www.yahoo.com/news/articles/chinese-hackers-bypassed-u-government-170949079.html?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xILmNvbS8&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAAD1nz5gdmjpxWS1JKDbXhHnijODBvGnTc0QvW

[K06STwKPHe4NbnqWV7Yuf4yYJuwD0sjVXkZ072_AHjLkA0fBybqIUvAutSIHZcYvfOu02VCBUeaBz_DaMU6GSb0YX5j9hHqWbwBPcqWU8A_c6a0DC7S0uBpZVIG6dKkjCu7](https://www.yahoo.com/news/articles/chinese-hackers-bypassed-u-government-170949079.html?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xILmNvbS8&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAAD1nz5gdmjpxWS1JKDbXhHnijODBvGnTc0QvW)

Cleaning up America's Backyard: The Overthrow of Guatemala's Arbenz. <https://adst.org/2016/06/cleaning-americas-backyard-outhrow-guatemalas-arbenz/>

Borzillo, L. (2023, 9 jan). *Taiwan and the "New Cold War"*. Network For Strategic Analysis (NSA). <https://ras-nsa.ca/taiwan-and-the-new-cold-war/#:~:text=At%20the%20strategic%20level%2C%20Taiwan,interest%20of%20the%20United%20States>

Asia for Educators, Columbia University. (s. f.). *Asia for Educators | Columbia University*.

https://afe.easia.columbia.edu/special/china_1950_us_china.htm#:~:text=Content:%201949%2D1971,especially%20Japan%20and%20South%20Korea

Global Taiwan Institute. (2025, mar 5). *Taiwan's Shortage of Chipmakers: A Major Threat to the Industry's Long-term Growth*. <https://globaltaiwan.org/2025/03/taiwansshortage-of-chipmakers-a-major-threat-to-the-industrys-long-term-growth/#:~:text=Taiwan's%20semiconductor%20sector%20has%20established,t%20a%20decline%20in%20revenue>

Reporter, G. S. (2022, sep 13). Russia has spent \$300m since 2014 to influence foreign officials, US says. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2022/sep/13/russia-foreign-election-interferencestate-department>

TRADING ECONOMICS. *United States exports by category*. <https://tradingeconomics.com/united-states/exports-by-category#:~:text=united%20states%2C%20Last%2C%20Previous%2C%20Highest%2C%20Lowest%2C%20Unit.,357.60%2C%20345.33%2C%20419.23%2C%200.58%2C%20USD%20Billion%2C%20%5B+%5D>

Taneja, H., & Zakaria, F. (2023, 6 sep). *AI and the New Digital Cold War*. Harvard Business Review. <https://hbr.org/2023/09/ai-and-the-new-digital-cold-war>

Allegations of espionage, theft add fuel to the fire in US-China chip war. <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/asia-pacific/allegations-of-espionage-theft-add-fuel-tothe-fire-in-us-china-chip-war/3654327>

The Multidimensional Impact of European Union Migration Policy on Mediterranean Countries

Ayşe Yayla

Rabia Günder

Migration has become one of the most significant challenges in contemporary international relations, particularly in Europe, where the Mediterranean serves as a major entry route for migrants and asylum seekers. The European Union created a complete migration policy which establishes border management and unified asylum procedures and third country partnership programs to solve these problems. The different operations in these processes received major support from Frontex and other agencies. The European Union migration policies present multiple effects which extend beyond security concerns to include economic, political and ethical impacts particularly in Mediterranean nations. The security-oriented policies which developed from these factors require investigation because they created economic, political and ethical consequences for both Spain and Italy.

The European Union migration policy, which places special emphasis on security and border control, establishes the main framework for managing migration in the European Union. Küçük (2021) explained through his research that the process of securitization establishes a system which treats migration as a potential threat to European social and political stability. The European Union established a security framework which protects its external borders against unauthorized migration through the Mediterranean area. The process establishes a direct connection between securitization and the belief that migration represents a danger to social order. Czaika and de Haas (2013) found that security policies developed through these frameworks show significant differences between their intended design and actual operational success. The European Union uses legal systems, which include shared asylum procedures, to establish the protocols that dictate how migrants will be treated within its borders. Additionally, it bases its migration policies on security-centered regulations, particularly affecting Mediterranean entry points in Spain and Italy.

Moreover, migration policies create their economic effects which develop special importance for Spain and Italy who belong to the Mediterranean region. The financial

situation of these countries receives negative effects because of their border control expenditures. The border management costs create a financial burden which EU member states must share according to Küçük (2021). The Mediterranean countries bear a greater financial burden than other regions. The governments must allocate funds to provide housing and medical services for the immigrant population. The EU provides financial assistance to immigrants through its multiple funding initiatives, yet this financial aid distribution remains unbalanced. The immigration process generates economic advantages for the economy through immigrant movement. The movement creates a solution to the existing labor deficit which affects the economy. Czaika and de Haas (2013) show that global migration patterns create economic impacts which result from their complex nature. The outcomes differ from what the original plan intended to achieve.

Furthermore, EU migration policies have a significant socio-political impact, especially in Mediterranean frontier states. This is evidenced by a study conducted by Çetin and Günsal (2025), which shows the impact of migration crises on "reshaping political discourse and policy priorities within the EU." This is characterized by a "securitization of migration," where migration is seen as a threat rather than a social issue. This, in turn, affects the views of the people, as emphasized by the European Commission, where "the EU should ensure that migration is managed in a human and efficient way." However, there are varying views about migration, as emphasized by the same source, where "Europeans' attitudes toward immigration are far from uniform." Furthermore, the unequal burden of migration policies also creates tensions, as emphasized by the same source, where "current policies place disproportionate responsibility on Mediterranean border states." This leads to polarization within the country and the rise of anti-immigration rhetoric, which, in turn, shapes national politics and underscores the need for a rights-based policy framework.

In addition, the European Union experiences major ethical problems for its migration policies because its policies "prioritize border security over humanitarian protection". The existing tension between "deterrence-based migration management strategies" and "externalization agreements with non-EU countries" creates problems for critics who claim these strategies "abuse the international solidarity principle". Islam et al. (2025) demonstrate that securitization practices "shift attention away from the protection of fundamental rights". The existing frameworks fail to recognize that "the drivers of migration are complex and multifaceted" because they include various factors

like poverty and conflict. The Mediterranean crossing movement demonstrates high human costs because it remains "one of the most hazardous migration routes in the world". The EU needs to control migration flows while maintaining "compliance with international law, European legal mechanisms, and fundamental human rights". The recent legal critiques show that "the readmission agreement between the EU and Turkey" creates problems for determining whether such agreements enable "compatible with the right to seek asylum". The border management system requires a "rights-based, adaptable framework" which protects human dignity according to its essential requirements.

Ultimately, The European Union maintains a restrictive migration system which treats border nations in the Mediterranean as its first defense line. The existing governance system creates fundamental rights violations because it prioritizes border security above basic human rights protection. The research shows that this method increases social divides while creating more anti-immigration remarks which do not resolve the complicated reasons behind migration. The system needs "binding responsibility-sharing mechanisms" together with "rights-based policy framework" which will achieve balance between border security and "humanitarian obligations". The successful management of migration requires countries to practice solidarity through equitable distribution of responsibilities.

References

Czaika, M., & de Haas, H. (2013). The effectiveness of immigration policies. *Population and Development Review*, 39(3), 487–508. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23655336>

Çetin, E., & Günsal, Z. (2025). The impact of the 2022 European Union migration crisis on the migratory discourses adopted by the European Parliament. *Uluslararası İlişkiler / International Relations*, 22(88), 83–100. <https://doi.org/10.33458/uidergisi.1761201>

Islam, M. S., Hasan, A. M., Ashraf, A., & Faisal, M. M. (2025). The Mediterranean migration crisis: A critical analysis of current legal mechanisms and policy responses of EU. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (58), 23–42. <https://doi.org/10.52642/susbed.1534681>

Küçük, A. (2021). The securitization of migration in the European Union. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (39), 205–224. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/susbed/article/1534681>

The Danish American Diplomatic Dispute over Greenland

Daniel Seweryn
Paula de la Rosa Gómez

Nowadays, the international stage is full of uncertainty and rapid changes that affect us as global citizens unexpectedly every day. For example, why would somebody expect that an island covered eighty percent by ice might become a diplomatic affair? Greenland, the world's largest island, is in the northeastern region of North America, between the Atlantic and Arctic Ocean. In fact, its strategic position makes it highly valuable on an international scale due to its mineral resources, Arctic shipping routes and military bases. Therefore, the United States declared its intentions to take control over Greenland for national security reasons, whereas Denmark has opposed to this demand.

The Geopolitical Importance of Greenland and its Natural Resources

As was mentioned, Greenland is rich in mineral resources such as zinc, lead, gold, iron, rare earth elements as well as oil and copper (*Ali y Duggal, 2026*), which mostly remain untouched. Particularly, these kinds of rare earths are highly used in contemporary high-tech industries. In the commercial field, it has significant potential for international maritime routes that surround its territory. Some of the most relevant are the Northern Sea Route, The Northwest Passage, and the Transpolar Sea Route. In military terms, Greenland hosts various operational forces including the permanent US Pituffik Space Base and other Danish military installations.

The United States' Intent to Control Greenland

Seven years ago, Donald Trump declared his intentions to buy this large island, while Denmark responded that *it was not for sale* (*Ali y Duggal, 2026*). A few months ago, the president of the United States reiterated this intention more forcefully. At first glance, it appears that Trump wants to provide Greenland with safety and contribute to its development and well-being. Nevertheless, Russian and Chinese influence on the island is rapidly growing in commercial terms and their activity can threaten the US economy. China, one of the world's biggest

economies, needs new connections to Europe; by sailing north, they would save 40% of the transportation distance, instead of sailing south. From China's perspective, the routes through Greenland are crucial. Furthermore, Russia holds its military bases in the Arctic and becomes more present in the region every year. According to the experts, this puts both America and NATO at risk (*Jacobsen, Wæver y Pram Gad, 2024*). Although the distances in the Arctic appear enormous, they are relatively short, making them merely fastballs for contemporary missiles.

Denmark's Relation with Greenland and its Outlook about the Intentions of United States

Throughout history, Greenland has been controlled by Denmark over three hundreds of years as an isolated and poor colony until the mid-20th century. After the American invasion, it was decided that the island finally belonged to the Kingdom of Denmark and as a result, the Greenlanders became Danish citizens. In 1979, a referendum on autonomy granted Greenland sovereignty in internal affairs such as education, health, and public administration. Denmark was granted the authority to take control over the foreign affairs, defense of the island, as well as to manage the economic subsidies received. Therefore, the role of Denmark in Greenland's functioning is essential for two reasons: the historical and legacy aspects and the capacity of giving economic and security benefits. Because of this diplomatic tension, the Danish Prime Minister, Mette Frederiksen rejected any idea of sale or adherence (*Reuters, 2025*).

The Political Point of View of Greenland

More than one thousand years ago, the Inuit, indigenous people of Greenland, came to the island and settled there. The culture of this population is diverse and focused on their spiritual relationship with nature. For example, hunting and fishing have always been an inseparable part of their cultural identity, economy, and community. Despite the autonomy that Greenland already has, there are several movements that want to gain independence and protect the natural environment. It is mainly due to the Danish colonial past, during which speaking their native language was forbidden and children were separated from their parents (*BBC, 2015*). Moreover, the Inuit consider that the fishing industry is a great part of the island

economy; as a result, many of them believe it could drive autonomous business without the presence of external actors. For all these reasons most of the Greenland population does not desire to become part of the United States. In fact, the current Prime Minister of Greenland, Jens-Frederik Nielsen, has publicly rejected any idea about annexing the island. However, there is still an internal debate about how strong their independence relationship with Denmark is.

After this discussion of the conflict surrounding Greenland, we have been able to verify what position the states have adopted and understand the complexity of their political and historical background. While United States seeks to strengthen its influence in the Arctic and protect its national interests, Denmark and Greenland demonstrate their disagreement about the issue of the island's sovereignty. Nevertheless, there are still tensions that need to be resolved. For instance, the matter of Greenland's independence and the possible conflict between the United States and NATO members. Finally, this controversy is another piece of evidence that shows how the order of international relations can be easily broken and fragmented.

References

BBC. (2015). *Denmark's Inuit Experiment*.
<https://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/p02tgfmh>

Marc Jacobsen, Ole Wæver, & Ulrik Pram Gad. (2024). *Greenland in Arctic Security (De)securitization Dynamics under Climatic Thaw and Geopolitical Freeze*. 196–226. <https://www.liverpooluniversitypress.co.uk/doi/pdf/10.3828/9780472076703#page=209>

Marium Ali & Hanna Duggal. (2026). *Greenland's strategic position in seven maps: Why Trump wants the island*.
<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2026/1/21/greenlands-strategic-position-in-seven-maps-why-trump-wants-the-island>

Reuters. (2025). *Denmark PM repeats that Greenland is not for sale*.
<https://www.reuters.com/world/denmark-pm-repeats-that-greenland-is-not-sale-2025-02-03/>

AI and AI-Based Disinformation and Its Impact on International Politics

Emirhan Demirci
Emirhan Can Akkoyun

People tend to think of using artificial intelligence in individual purposes but have you ever wondered how artificial intelligence is being used in globally? In early 21st century through a survey and events conducted mainly by Alan Turing in England has resulted in AI's development (Copeland, 2026). "AI is the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings." (Copeland, 2026). Artificial intelligence has been utilized both in everyday and global aspects such as web searching, advertising, cybersecurity and health. However, it's progression causes unexpected results like some corrupted politicians utilizing ai to create disinformation. Therefore, malicious use of artificial intelligence reduces the reliability in international politics.

Firstly, the usage of artificial intelligence reduces the reliability in elections by creating disinformation. According to López-Borrull and Lopezosa(2025), disinformation and propaganda in the politics refers to the deceitful and misused information to manipulate public opinion. Artificial intelligence has become a tool of convenience for politicians' propaganda or content generation in recent years. "In the unusually concentrated wave of elections that took place in 2024, A.I. was used in more than 80 percent..." (Myers & Thompson, 2025.) With the advancement in technology and AI, propagandists shifted the aspects of AI's benefits to their advantage with creating deepfake or similar techniques. A good example for this would be; "Shortly before the parliamentary elections in Slovakia, a deepfake audio recording surfaced on the internet, falsely portraying the leader of Progressive Slovakia, Michal Šimečka, as engaged in a conversation with a journalist about how to rig the elections." (Myers & Thompson, 2025.) On account of this, even though the main reasons for AI's progress was meant to be in a good intention, in some areas like politics, it has been used for deepfakes, misinformation and manipulation.

Furthermore, False Accusations has a new way of occurring by widespread usage of AI. Global and open access to the AI has caused people to use it however they wanted. According to research shared by Microsoft (2026), in the second half of the 2025 year, nearly one in six people are now using generative AI tools. As AI becomes more accessible, it becomes easier to generate convincing content. These contents could include manipulated or misleading aspects that may cause disinformation intentionally or unintentionally. In International politics, this type of information would be spread rapidly due to the intriguing nature of disinformation. A real-life example for this situation has occurred during Ukrainian-Russian war. According to a report of Reuters (2022) "A poorly edited video purporting to show Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelenskiy publicly capitulating to Russian demands drew widespread ridicule". This video was labeled deepfake later but, it has shown us how misleading generative AI tools can be used and affect international politics badly. Consequently, it shows how AI-generated misinformation can damage trust and create serious issues in international politics.

Another important point is that, artificial intelligence can be used as a tool of warfare to distort information and deceive people. In modern information warfare, the role of artificial intelligence has become crucial and its importance continues to increase rapidly. Consequently, misinformation, which is created with the help of AI, is being used in international conflicts to manipulate the public opinion. For instance, during the Russia-Ukraine war, several deepfake videos of Zelenskyy that falsely shows him ordering Ukrainian soldiers to surrender started to emerge online. Although those videos were quickly labeled as fake, they also managed to lead many people to believe they were real. This ultimately reduced individuals' morale, as well as confusing them and creating chaos (Holroyd & Olorunselu, 2022). To give another example, according to AFP Fact Check, AI-generated videos were used to falsely demonstrate Iranian missiles striking Tel Aviv during the Iran-Israel war. These AI-generated videos significantly contributed creating fear among people. To summarize, the misuse of artificial intelligence in creating misinformation has a great role in causing fear, deception and confusion among societies.

To conclude, reliability in international politics for AI is rapidly declining because of the misuse of AI. The advancement in technology and AI created an opportunity for politicians or government authorities to use AI to their advantage by creating deepfake or similar techniques. As in the example of The Russian-Ukrainian conflict, AI has also been used to inflict confusion and fear to create disruption and chaos in societies. All

things considered, if artificial intelligence continues to be used as a tool to create disinformation in international politics, how can humanity be able to trust any information they encounter on internet in the future?

References

Azgin, B., & Kiralp, S. (2024). Surveillance, Disinformation, and Legislative Measures in the 21st Century: AI, Social Media, and the Future of Democracies. *Social Sciences*, 13(10), 510.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci13100510>

Copeland, B. (2026, February 18). history of artificial intelligence (AI). Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/science/history-of-artificial-intelligence>

Holroyd, M., & Olorunselu, F. (2022, March 16). *Deepfake Zelenskyy surrender video is the 'first intentionally used' in Ukraine war*. EuroNews.

<https://www.euronews.com/my-europe/2022/03/16/deepfake-zelenskyy-surrender-video-is-the-first-intentionally-used-in-ukraine-war>

López-Borrull, A., & Lopezosa, C. (2025). Mapping the Impact of Generative AI on Disinformation: Insights from a Scoping Review. *Publications*, 13(3), 33. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications13030033>

Microsoft Corporate Blogs (2026, January 8). *Global AI Adoption in 2025 A Widening Digital Divide*. Microsoft. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/Microsoft-AI-Diffusion-Report-2025-H2.pdf>

Myers, S. L., & Thompson, S. A. (2025, June 26). *A.I. Is Starting to Wear Down Democracy*. The New York Times.

<https://www.nytimes.com/2025/06/26/technology/ai-elections-democracy.html>

Pearson, J., & Zinets, N. (2022, March 16). *Deepfake footage purports to show Ukrainian president capitulating*. Reuters.

<https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/deepfake-footage-purports-show-ukrainian-president-capitulating-2022-03-16/>

Türkiye's Political Stance in the Russia-Ukraine War

Prince Mboungou

Esmanur Sultan Toklucu

For decades, Türkiye has been playing a key role among countries in its region, on the issue of the Black Sea Region; the same case applies to the Russian-Ukrainian conflict that has been ongoing since 2022. The war between Russia and Ukraine has placed Ankara in a particularly delicate position, forcing it to balance its western commitments with its close relations with Moscow. Türkiye as, the only NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) member with a Black Sea coastline is in a very strategic location. Ankara condemned Russia's invasion and reaffirmed its support for Ukraine's territorial integrity, while refraining from fully aligning with Western sanctions against Russia. This posture aims to preserve Türkiye's economic, energy, and security interests while maintaining its credibility as a mediator. It is important to see to what extent Türkiye impacts this conflict.

This article examines Türkiye's role in the Russia-Ukraine war and its consequences regarding Türkiye's stability.

Türkiye's Relationship with Russia-Ukraine Pre-war and Post-war. Relationship with Russia-Ukraine Pre-war

The two countries have developed a strategic partnership in energy (natural gas and nuclear power), trade, and tourism. However, they have also found themselves on opposing sides in regional conflicts, including Syria, Libya, and the South Caucasus. After 2022, Ankara sought to keep communication channels open. Türkiye did not implement Western sanctions and became an important economic space for Russian companies. By not fully aligning with Western sanctions Türkiye has both safeguarded its own energy needs and served as a secure trade gateway for Russian companies (Örmeci et al., 2025). This situation has ensured that Ankara has not severed its ties with Moscow, thereby establishing Türkiye as a reliable interlocutor in Russia's eyes (Örmeci et al., 2025)

Relations During the Invasion of Ukraine

Turkish-Ukrainian relations intensified before the war, particularly in the defense sector. Türkiye supported Ukraine's sovereignty, including its position on Crimea. After Russia's invasion, Ankara continued its political and military support for Kyiv while simultaneously acting as a mediator. A significant example of this is its involvement in negotiations and prisoner exchanges, which were publicly acknowledged by Ukrainian authorities.

The Republic of Türkiye is one of Ukraine's key and traditionally significant trading partners in the region (Zharova, 2025). Türkiye played a key role in the Black Sea grain initiatives, facilitating Ukrainian grain exports.

The most concrete example of Türkiye's success in this war is the major prisoner exchange that took place in September 2022. This event demonstrated to the whole world that Türkiye is the only power capable of sitting down at the negotiating table with both countries (Anadolu Agency, 2022)

Ukrainian Refugees in Türkiye

Since 2022, Türkiye has hosted a significant number of Ukrainian refugees. However, the country was already one of the world's leading refugee-hosting states, particularly concerning Syrians. Despite this, they established temporary protection mechanisms for Ukrainians. Hosting Ukrainian refugees aligns with Ankara's intention to maintain its image as a responsible humanitarian power while reinforcing bilateral relations. As a result, providing protection for Ukrainian people reinforces Ankara's role as a responsible power, and this support improves mutual trust between two nations.

Türkiye's Support of the Ukrainian Military

During Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, the two countries significantly deepened their cooperation in the military-technical sphere, especially after 2014, including in the supply of UAVs, armored vehicles, missile systems, and engines for aviation equipment. They are establishing joint enterprises and production projects and strengthening the defense capabilities of both states (Zharova,2025). Turkey's military cooperation with Ukraine is not limited to UAVs; since 2014, joint projects have been carried out across many areas, such as armored vehicles and aircraft engines (Zahore & Khlobysytov, 2025). Furthermore, it is expected that Turkish companies intend to a

very significant role in Ukraine's reconstruction following the end of the war (Zahora & Khlobystov, 2025).

Russia-Türkiye Relationship in the Black Sea Region During the War

The Black Sea represents a crucial strategic space, and Türkiye's control over the Bosphorus and Dardanelles straits is governed by the 1936 Montreux Convention, which grants Ankara a central role in regulating the passage of military vessels. Although it is widely recognized that "before the war, the Black Sea was already as arena of strategic competition between Russia and NATO" the current conflict has increased the significance of this role. Consequently, Türkiye's decision to follow the Montreux rules strictly results in a safer environment, leading to more stability in the Black Sea.

Conclusion

Türkiye's position in the Russia-Ukraine war illustrates a pragmatic and multidimensional diplomacy. The war has compelled Ankara to maintain a delicate balance between its commitments to the West, particularly as a member of NATO, and its economic, energy, and political relations with Moscow. Rather than fully aligning with one side, Türkiye has pursued a pragmatic strategy that allows it to support Ukraine's sovereignty while preserving dialogue and cooperation with Russia.

Through its diplomatic mediation, humanitarian assistance, and control over the strategic straits under the Montreux Convention, Türkiye has demonstrated its ability to act as a key regional power capable of communicating with both parties. This balanced approach has helped Ankara maintain its strategic autonomy while reinforcing its international relevance.

However, this position also carries long-term challenges. Maintaining such a careful equilibrium may become increasingly difficult if tensions between Russia and Western allies intensify further. The future of the conflict will therefore test Türkiye's diplomatic flexibility and its capacity to remain a credible mediator.

Ultimately, the question remains: can Türkiye continue to balance these competing interests while preserving both its regional stability and its role as a bridge between rival geopolitical blocs?

References

- Düs, A. N. (2022, September 22). Ukraine thanks Türkiye for support in Russia-Ukraine prisoner swap. Anadolu Agency. <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2716719575?pq-origsite=primo&accountid=14778&RAO=true&searchKeywords=T%C3%BCrkiye%2520Russia%2520Ukraine&sourcetype=Wire%2520Feeds>
- Erkem Gülboy, P., & Çoruk, E. (2024). Pursuing sustainable development goals: the performance of Türkiye in the centennial of the Republic (H. D. Mumcu Akan, F. Karagöz Özenç, Ö. Garan & B. Engin Özenç, Eds.). İstanbul University Press. https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/312688/1/Istanbul-University-Press_9786050716108.pdf#page=746
- Ketenci, A. (2023). Russia's war on Ukraine and the Montreux Convention as Türkiye's international law instrument and policy tool for the security of the Black Sea. *Connections: The Quarterly Journal* (English Edition), 22(3). <https://doi.org/10.11610/Connections.22.3.07>
- Örmeci, O., Uğşal, O., & Yorulmaz, M. (2025). Turkish-Russian relations in the post-Cold War period.. Transnational Press London. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ozan-Oermeci/publication/398031077_-_OrmeciozanYorulmazMuratUksalOlgun2025Turkish-RussianRelationsinthePostColdWarPeriodinContemporaryTurkish-RussianRelationsinthe21stCenturyGlobalGeopoliticsedsbyOzanOrmeciozanYorulmazMuratUksalOlgun2025Turkish-RussianRelationsinthePostColdWarPeriodinContemporaryTurkish-RussianRelationsinthe21stCenturyGlobalGeopoliticsedsbyOz.pdf
- Ulas, G. (2026). Türkiye's strategic ambiguity in the Russia-Ukraine war. *Small Wars & Insurgencies*, 37(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592318.2025.2607400>
- Zahora, L., & Khlobystov, I. (2025). Ukraine-Turkey economic and socio-political relations: trends, prospects and post-war risks. *European Scientific Journal of Economic and Financial Innovation*. <https://www.journal.eae.com.ua/index.php/journal/article/download/667/507>

Can a Neutral Language Save International Law?

Eva Rodríguez Díez

“You need to learn English if you want a future.” Most people have probably heard this statement more than once, at school, in a family setting, by colleagues and strangers alike. Nowadays, it is typical to enrol young children in extra English classes outside of school while they are young, all to give them a leg-up in life. Some universities even require an English diploma to finish your degree, as becoming well-educated and getting a good job nowadays has become virtually impossible without having a working knowledge of this language. English was long ago proclaimed as a default international language that everyone in the world is expected to know, but has this created an unfair disadvantage for other languages in the international scene? How we can remedy this is what will be discussed in this article.

Language bias in international law

The Oxford English Dictionary defines a bias as an “inclination or prejudice for or against one person or group, especially in a way considered to be unfair”. (Oxford English Dictionary, s. f.). So, according to this source, a language bias is one whose basis resides in favouring those who speak a certain language, at the expense of those who do not. In theory, many international institutions will deny the idea of there being such a linguistic bias in international law. For example, the United Nations (UN) actively battles this bias by having six official languages: Arabic, English, French, Russian, Spanish and Mandarin.

Furthermore, the institution prides itself on its active involvement to ensure equitable treatment and eliminate disparity by setting minimum standards for all of their organs to follow. These include the idea of there not being a focus on just translating, but also always following the highest grammatical standards for each of the languages, which must always appear in alphabetical order to avoid favouritisms. (Committee on Information, 2025). Another example, is the Statute of the International Court of Justice in its article 38.1d ensures using “teachings of the most highly qualified publicists of various nations” as auxiliary means in their work (ICJ, s. f.).

However, these aspects mostly stay in theory and do not translate into practice. Despite the UN's linguistic ambitions, its website is more commonly used in English, according to research done by the UN, with 47.8% of visitors to the website choosing the said language. This is almost double the second most used tongue, Spanish, with a 25.4%. (Committee on Information, 2025). Similarly, and in contradiction with the ICJ's statute, of the ten most cited writers in ICJ's case law, six of them are British and one of them is from the U.S. (Fikfak et al., 2022). English and French may be the official working languages for institutions such as the UN, the ICJ and the International Criminal Court. However, the truth is that, from April 2014 to March 2015, out of the 401 international law books published, 340 were in English (84.8%)(Fikfak et al., 2022).

The reality is that English speakers and written works have it easier to thrive in international law, and although this may not seem harmful, it causes several disadvantages towards other languages. For example, each language is connected to a culture, and each person's culture defines the way they think. Therefore, different language speakers may interpret things in various ways, so fewer languages leads to less unique knowledge (Eco, s. f.). Many may think translations can solve these issues. In fact, it appears to be as easy as ever with the rise in use of artificial intelligence (AI). Nevertheless, each language carries within the meanings of words, interpretations often unique to the culture, which AI, and often even humans, cannot grasp unless fully immersed in the language and its culture. These language barriers have sometimes led to actual legal issues. For instance, in the case of *R. v. Iqbal Begum*, the defendant unknowingly plead guilty to murder because their translator did not speak the same dialect. By the time the Court realised this and ruled it as a mistrial, Begum had committed suicide (Eco, s. f.) (*R v. Iqbal Begum*, s. f.).

Therefore, the preference towards English in international law has caused a great disadvantage for those who either do not speak the language, or are not native speakers (Fikfak et al., 2022).

What can we do to fix this?

A solution is greatly needed. But, what can be done? Many experts agree that change starts with each individual. Researchers should be motivated to publish their work in their native language, although this may risk their ability to reach a broader

audience. As mentioned before, different languages are crucial for variations in scholar perspectives. This is precisely why institutions and states alike should actively work towards linguistic diversity, not only in theory, but also putting it to practice (Eco, s. f.).

Moreover, there needs to be more benefits to being a polyglot. Currently, those with English as their native tongue do not have an incentive for learning another language, like people in other countries do. This is shown by the fact that, 90% of adults in the EU know at least one foreign language in addition to their native one (EuroStat, s. f.), whereas 16.9% of adult Americans do the same (AMACAD, s. f.). This is not only harmful for research on the international stage, but also for the citizens who do not benefit from the gifts that multilingualism brings, such as better memory, communication skills, concentration and creativity. (Cambridge, s. f.).

So, what could be done to promote the study of more languages? One solution that has been debated for a few decades is the possibility of creating a new international neutral language, for people to learn as their second tongue. This would incentive people to learn a new language and it would help with the current inequality in international law, since it would be a second language for everyone. However, there are several conditions this new language would have to meet, such as it being easy to learn for all languages and being accessible for everyone to avoid further discrimination (Eco, s. f.).

Nevertheless, this is not a new idea. It would not be the first time such project is attempted. In 1887, a Polish man called L.L. Zamenhof published the first book of Esperanto grammar, *Unua Libro*, with the goal of achieving a universal union through a common language. Since then, its popularity grew exponentially. Esperanto literally translates to “one who hopes,” and many people hoped for a global language that could unite everyone around the world. Clubs started to be created worldwide, and many works of literature were translated to show Esperanto’s versatility and utility. In fact, an international organisation, the Universal Esperanto Association, was created in 1908 and there was even a monthly magazine in Germany called “*The Esperantisto*.” In 1905, the First World Esperanto Conference took place, at which it was firmly declared that Esperanto was not aimed to replace the existing national languages, which was a big concern at the time. Unlike other languages created with this same objective in mind, such as Volapük, Esperanto prided itself in its grammatical simplicity, being able to be learnt with ease from any language (Eco, s. f.).

Why did Esperanto not work?

However, times turned dark, and as it happened to so many other fields, its shadow began to cast over Esperanto. Extremist movements began to rise, and Esperanto was just one of many persecuted aspects of life (Cull, s. f.).

First, it started with Nazism. As Esperanto's creator was Jewish, Adolf Hitler, in his book, *Mein Kampf*, accused Jewish people of imposing Esperanto on others as one more step in their plan for world domination (Hitler, 1929). Despite many efforts to withdraw Esperanto from any type of political ideology, it was still strongly linked to Judaism, Socialism and Anarchism. Therefore, many speakers were sent to concentration camps, where, as an act of resistance, they started teaching other prisoners the language, while pretending to teach them Italian (Cull, s. f.).

Meanwhile, in 1929, a British journalist reported there were approximately 16,000 Esperanto speakers in the USSR, and this language being in fourth place of most taught in schools. In addition, it was commonly used when exchanging letters with foreigners. However, while Stalin was in power, the government discovered Russians were often asking questions on how life was outside the USSR, which could lead to them learning of better conditions elsewhere, possibly ending in a rebellion. At first, they just tried to control what could be written in the letters, but they soon banned Esperanto altogether, under the pretext of Russian prevalence (Nordenstorm, s. f.).

On top of this oppression, many scholars give several other reasons for Esperanto's fall. As it was mentioned above, languages are not just words put together, but each expression, each form of telling a story, is deeply influenced by culture. Centuries of evolution have created the tongues known today, and every common phrase, every way of ordering thoughts, comes from ages of cultural influence. That is why, for example, some languages have words or phrases whose origin is different from others, due to decades of cultural integration all throughout history. (Tonkin, 2015).

However, Esperanto is an artificial language. It was created lacking that cultural background and evolution. That is precisely why many professionals, such as the critic Ludwig Wittgenstein, argue that Esperanto lacks the emotion required for the language to stick. Let's think for a second about when we learn a new language. The first thing most people learn, and the easiest to remember, are often curse words. That is because there is a strong emotion behind them, which makes them resonate with us more,

therefore making them more memorable. Nevertheless, Esperanto does not have that natural emotion behind it, making it unappealing and unmemorable. (Tonkin, 2015).

On top of that, English has positioned itself as the unofficial lingua franca in the globalised world. At first, England's military and economic power, by which it acquired such an empire, helped extend English as a language, which was reinforced by the rise of the U.S. as a global power. Soon, it was not just the tongue, but also the culture, exactly what Esperanto lacked, which became an emblem world-wide, leaving Esperanto long forgotten (Fikfak et al., 2022).

Those aspects, alongside the strains that emerged inside the Esperanto community due to reformist ideals, were the final blow that separated Esperanto from the dream Zamenhof had made public in 1887 (Eco, s. f.).

The dangers of a neutral language

However, there are many people all around the world who still have hope for a neutral language, whether it is Esperanto or something else. But many scholars have pointed out the dangers of actually creating a working neutral language, aside from the current national ones.

The first worry is the risk it poses for minor languages. The rise of a tongue spoken worldwide will shift learning focus away from smaller languages. Resources will likely be directed towards teaching this global language, leaving speakers of minor ones to fend for themselves. According to the UN, there are currently around 3,000 languages in danger of disappearing within the 21st century (UNESCO, 2024). This can have grave consequences for the global scheme. For example, when languages from populations deep in the Amazon Rainforest, isolated from the outside world, disappeared, plenty of centuries-old knowledge about plants in the area that had been passed orally from one generation to the next, was lost with it (Štefić, s. f.).

In addition, as mentioned above, different languages are connected to and influenced by different cultures with various ways of viewing the world. Therefore, the death of tongues leads to the loss of knowledge itself, to the restriction of idea framing (Eco, s. f.).

Furthermore, it is necessary for everyone to access this language learning equally. If not, there will be, once again, as it is the current situation with English, an elite who dominates the language way better than others, causing a new bias, just in a different font (Štefić, s. f.).

Moreover, if people do not find enough advantages to being bilingual, there will be a progressive rise in those who only know this new neutral language, learning it as a native language, and therefore defeating its whole purpose.

So, despite the idea of a global language being the most optimistic solution for the current language bias in international law, there are plenty of risks to account for.

In essence, English is currently an unofficial lingua franca in international relations, which has unfortunately caused a bias in international law, as it is expected to be fluently known by everyone, disregarding other tongues. Many have thought of the creation of a neutral language as a possible solution. However, previous attempts have proven unsuccessful for various reasons, and scholars have studied the many risks of such an answer. Nevertheless, a resolution is still needed. So, the question remains, what could this answer could be?

References

Cambridge. (s. f.). *How learning a new language changes your brain*. Recuperado <https://www.cambridge.org/elt/blog/2022/04/29/learning-language-changes-your-brain/>

Committee on Information, G. A., United Nations. (2025, mayo 28). *Report of the Secretary-General*.

Cull, A. E. (s. f.). *Schism and Suppression: Early Threats to the Esperanto Language, and Resulting Impacts on International Acceptance*.

Eco, U. (s. f.). *La búsqueda de la lengua perfecta [11343]*.

EuroStat. (s. f.). *Foreign language skills statistics*. Recuperado https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Foreign_language_skills_statistics

Fikfak, V., Peat, D., & Van Der Zee, E. (2022). Bias in International Law. *German Law Journal*, 23(3), 281-297. <https://doi.org/10.1017/glj.2022.23>

Hitler, A. (s. f.). *Mi Lucha*. Recuperado <https://cdn.cienciapolitica.usac.glifos.net/digital/e9.pdf>

ICJ. (s. f.). *ICJ Statute*. Recuperado <https://www.icj-cij.org/statute>

Nordenstorm, L. (s. f.). *Recenzo pri nova eldono de studo pri la persekutoj kontraŭ Esperanto verkita de Ulrich Lins*. Recuperado <https://interlingvistiko.net/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/4-Nordenstorm.-Nova-eldono-de-studo-pri-la-persekutoj-kontraux-Esperanto.-Recenzo.pdf>

Oxford Dictionary. (s. f.). *Bias definition*. Recuperado <https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=bias>

R v. Iqbal Begum. (s. f.).

Štefić, A. (s. f.). *Dangers of a global language*.

Tonkin, H. (2015). Language Planning and Planned Languages: How Can Planned Languages Inform Language Planning? *Interdisciplinary Description of Complex Systems*, 13(2), 193-199. <https://doi.org/10.7906/indec.13.2.1>

UNESCO. (s. f.). *Multilingual education, the bet to preserve indigenous languages and justice*. Recuperado <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/multilingual-education-bet-preserve-indigenous-languages-and-justice>

Can We Stay Human in a World of War?

Iván Labarta Jaria

Some people think that wars are something that happened in the past and are no longer part of our reality. However, this belief could not be further from the truth. Around the world, conflicts continue to affect millions of people, creating a cycle of violence, suffering, and loss. Wars are not only political events, but they are also human tragedies that expose the darkest sides of society. One of the most alarming consequences of war is the process of dehumanization, where individuals are deprived of their basic human rights (Haslam, 2006).

Wars are often framed as tools for political gain or national defense, but they rarely benefit the general population. Political violence is often justified by leaders as needed to protect and expand a nation's security, territory or ideology. However, as Arendt argues, "violence can be justifiable, but it never will be legitimate" (Arendt, 1970). Still, it's the citizens who ultimately pay for these choices. Families are displaced, economies collapse, and communities are destroyed. "War is a racket" is what the U.S. Marine Corps Major General Smedley D. Butler said (Butler, 2003), and it can be reinterpreted as "war is a game for a few and it exploits the many". This gap between political goals and human outcomes shows how dehumanization begins even at the conceptual stage of war, at which point people are reduced to chess pieces in wider strategic aims. In warfare, human agents are seen as disposable resource assets in the pursuit of strategic goals.

Blockades of basic resources to a population during war in order to weaken the population and strive for economic pressure is clearly another way to show this dehumanization at the time. A current example of the devastating human cost of conflict is the ongoing conflict between Russia and Ukraine. Russia's blockades of basic resources such as water, food, medicine, or hygiene products are debilitating the civilians that could not migrate (Human Rights Watch, 2022). As a result, entire cities have faced shortages of essential supplies, leading to malnutrition or illness. These tactics not only target infrastructure but also attack the dignity of the population. Dehumanization is evident when access to the most basic human needs is deliberately restricted as a weapon of war.

The effects of war are not only physical but also deeply psychological. Soldiers on the front lines experience constant stress, fear, and trauma that they are not aware of at the moment, however it hits them hard throughout their post-war lives. This can result in long-term mental health issues such as PTSD (post-traumatic stress disorder). And not just to the soldiers, also civilians, face anxiety, depression, and a sense of helplessness. The constant exposure to violence alters behavior and perception. War has been shown to alter individual behavior and social functioning, often reducing people to survival mechanisms, eroding the human qualities that allow societies to function peacefully. This idea is reflected in testimonies from veterans, who often report quotes as: "In war, there are no unwounded soldiers". - José Narosky.

Furthermore, related to the last paragraph, we must talk about the crucial impact of this way of acting on victims. This just strips their sense of self and societal value. People lose not only their lives or families but their dignity, identity, value and human rights, as I mentioned at the introduction of the essay. Due to this conflict, they are often treated as objects or obstacles and not as what they are, humans with emotions and aspirations. In extreme cases dehumanization may justify torture, forced displacement, or even sexual violence (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2025). The moral and ethical consequences extend beyond the battlefield, leaving scars in societies that last for generations.

Wars are often accompanied by a flood of propaganda that manipulates public perception and shapes social attitudes. Governments and armed groups use media, advertisements, and social networks to portray the enemy as dangerous, inferior, or less than human, which makes it easier for populations to support aggressive policies. "Dehumanization enables us to regard others as less than human and thus makes violence against them seem acceptable." (Smith, 2011).

Dehumanization can happen off the battlefield too, in social media. Online platforms often reduce complex human beings into profiles, statistics, or fleeting comments, which makes it easier to ignore their feelings and experiences. Negative interactions, hostility, or bullying desensitize people to suffering. These daily patterns echo the processes seen in war, showing how societal dehumanization can normalize cruelty and diminish respect for others' dignity. For instance, disinformation campaigns have been widely documented in conflicts such as the Russia-Ukraine war, mentioned before, where digital media has played a key role in shaping international and domestic

perceptions (European External Action Service, 2023). Therefore, rather than merely reflecting dehumanization, social media actively contributes to the dynamics of modern warfare, extending the battlefield into the digital sphere.

In conclusion, war is not a distant historical phenomenon but a contemporary reality that continues to dehumanize millions. From political operations to blockades, psychological trauma, and violations of basic rights, the human cost is profound. Recognizing the process of dehumanization is essential to preserving empathy and humanity even in the midst of conflict. By remembering the essential value of every individual, societies can strive toward peace, justice, and the protection of human dignity principles that war so often threatens to destroy.

Just to end this essay, I would like to give you an example I wrote a year ago about humanization and dehumanization that worked perfectly at the time and may work as well here. Humanity is the one that each of us makes up, all the human being. That man you see walking his dog every morning, or that girl you see reading in the park. Both are parts of this word that encompasses but also separates. Because now, that man who was walking his dog is on the news. "Dog abandoned in a landfill". That's what you hear on the news, and then, that same man who previously seemed super responsible and humane walking his dog every morning, becomes a terrible person, cruel and heartless, who paradoxically, lacks humanity, lacks that human nature. The lack of humanity is the lack of empathy. This stems from our pride, arrogance, and greed. And this is how misanthropy came to be, which involves a negative judgment about the flaws of humanity. And this is what we often base our judgments on. Therefore, that man walking his dog at the beginning of this paragraph, seen on the news, should not we have spoken to him before judging the situation? Or could not the reporters themselves have done so? Perhaps, instead of the owner, it is these reporters who are truly representing the lack of humanity in society by judging this lack of humanity without having reliable information and without speaking to this person.

That was just an example of a part of dehumanization outside the war context, but it shows that maybe we should consider other perspectives to judge and to act. Could the government try to solve their differences without exposing the population? Could they do it without depriving the people of their basic human rights? I do not know, but maybe that is what the global opinion and countries could work on.

References

Arendt, H. (1970). *On Violence*. New York: Harcourt, Brace & Company. <https://www.penguin.co.uk/books/455313/on-violence-by-arendt-hannah/9780241631645>

Butler. (1935). *War is a racket*. https://www.heritage-history.com/site/hclass/secret_societies/ebooks/pdf/butler_racket.pdf

European External Action Service (2023). *Disinformation and Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine*. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/information-integrity-and-counteracting-foreign-information-manipulation-interference-fimi_en

Haslam, Nick. (2006). *An integrative review*. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*. https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1207/s15327957pspr1003_4

Human Rights Watch. (2022, March 21). *Ukraine: Ensure safe passage, aid for Mariupol civilians*. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/03/21/ukraine-ensure-safe-passage-aid-mariupol-civilians>

Picador. (2011). *The Paperbark Tree* by Goldie Goldbloom. https://www.bookbrowse.com/quotes/detail/index.cfm/quote_number/464/in-war-there-are-no-unwounded-soldiers

Smith, D. L. (2011). *Less Than Human: Why We Demean, Enslave, and Exterminate Others*. St. Martin's Press. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2710791>

Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. (2025). *Dehumanization*. In Edward N. Zalta, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2025 Edition). <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/dehumanization/>

The 2026 American-Israeli Attack on Iran

Pedro Manuel Fanego Díaz

Introduction

The attack of February 28th to early March has caused great confusion in many people around the world, why a president who campaigned in non-intervention is starting a new war, and particularly in the Middle East? What is exactly the problem the US and Israel have with Iran? Why Iran has the government type it has? Those questions are indicative of a very poor job at making the public knowledgeable of such important events, and my article is aimed at clarifying the *mysteries* many people face regarding the current state of conflict.

Reviewing the events

In January of 2026, protests against the Iranian government were held by the opposition inside that country, shortly after, in February, nuclear energy negotiations between the USA and Iran were held in neutral Oman, but they ended in failure.

This convoluted scenario, alongside Israeli pressure on the Trump administration (Iran is a real threat to Israel more so than to the US), was the key motivation for an open conflict.

The war started on 28th February (coinciding with the Muslim festivity of Ramadan, a month long fast during day hours) with a series of airstrikes by the US Air Force and the Israeli Air Force. Among those attacks, an infamous one was the Minab school attack (Feb 28th), alongside the assassination of Supreme Leader Ali Khamenei and other top officials like Aziz Nasirzadeh (minister of defence).

Continuous attacks followed in the next weeks from the American-Israeli side, but also the Iranian counterattacks started, and were mainly targeted at Israel, various gulf countries (like Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Bahrain ...) and the British overseas territory of Akrotiri and Dhekelia in Cyprus (two British military bases), French troops in northern Iraq were also targeted.

After Iran's President Masoud Pezeshkian disappeared, Vice President Mohammad Reza Aref briefly took control of the country before Pezeshkian and two senior Ayatollahs (top ranking Shiite clerics) Gholam-Hossein Mohseni-Eje'i and Alireza Arafii formed the Interim Leadership Council and chose on March 8th Khamenei's son, Mojtaba Khamenei, as new Supreme Leader.

History as guide to the present

Iran is quite an old country, while they have always used that name, in the West most people used "Persia" until not so long ago. Today that name is mostly used to refer to the Classical period Empires that originated in that region. I could write thousands of books about just that part of Iranian history, but this article is mostly focused on the critical events related to today's conflicts.

For most of the Middle Ages, Iran was ruled by foreign empires and dynasties, alongside the progressive conversion of the population to Islam. It wasn't until the 1500s where the Safavid dynasty transforms it into an imperial power who also made Shia Islam the state religion. Its end came in the mid-to-late 1700s, when general Nader Afsharid established a short-lived dynasty that collapsed with his death, which was followed by a short warlord period that ended with the Qajar dynasty taking power and ruling through the 1800s and the early 20th century.

The Qajar dynasty, however, was caught in the dual imperial ambitions of Russia and Great Britain (labelled "Great Game") to control the Asian continent. Since Russia attacked them directly on various occasions, Iranian politics started to shift towards appeasing Great Britain in order to prevent direct Russian aggression. This proved detrimental in the long run, as British influence over Iranian politics and economy soon grew to a quasi-colonial level, most notorious is the establishment of the Anglo-Persian Oil Company, which was granted by the Qajar monarch the right to own and exploit all oil in the country in exchange for minimal revenue paid to the monarch's treasure.

The start of the end for the Qajars was the Russo-British invasion in 1915 during World War 1, the incapability of the Shah to prevent the invasion (and his young age) left the country demoralized and severely weakened (a famine which killed between 2 and 9 million people took place during occupation). This state of

affairs prompted General Reza Khan to organize a coup d'etat in 1921, proclaiming himself Shah (monarch) of the new Pahlavi dynasty and establishing a modernizer regime. Said regime lasted until WW2 when Iran was invaded by Great Britain and the USSR. They wanted to remove Reza Pahlavi from power due to his government's ties to Germany. After the war a brief period of parliamentary ruled unfolded due to the new Shah, Mohammad Reza Pahlavi, living in Rome.

The parliamentary period ended shortly after the election of Mohammad Mosadegh as Prime Minister and his nationalization of oil. This caused British and American secret services to orchestrate a coup against his government. After which was proclaimed the personal government of Shah Mohammad Reza Pahlavi.

Pahlavi established an authoritarian one-party state lead by himself and enacted forced westernization programmes (such as banning the Islamic veil, replacing the Islamic calendar with the Gregorian calendar, etc). He also organized a state-capitalist economy with oil revenues that he funnelled into industrial projects and into lavish monuments and royal parties. However, it was his policy of price controls towards bazaars (self-employed merchants) which caused massive unrest in the country, which was already increasing due to popular disapproval of the secret services' (SAVAK) actions against the opposition.

The unrest was channelled by various opposition factions, among them, Rudollah Khomeini's Islamist circle managed to mobilize the Shiite clergy and other discontent groups (most notably bazaar merchants) and other opposition factions to paralyse the country. Mohammad Shah left the country in 1979 to seek treatment for his cancer illness. As the country was uncontrollable by his government, it was interpreted as an escape and Khomeini flew back from his exile in Paris and took power.

Khomeini established an Islamic Republic, a government of republican form but in which the Shiite clergy would serve as a class of guardians, headed by himself as Supreme Leader. This position would act as a supervisor with veto power against parliamentary decisions. Shortly after the Islamic Revolution, Saddam Hussein's Iraq invaded Iran taking advantage of the instability in the new

state. The war ended in a draw after 9 years and Khomeini died the next year. He was succeeded by Ali Khamenei as new Supreme Leader.

The Islamic Republic has ruled the country ever since, and among the legalized political groups there are roughly two factions: the conservative “principlists” represent the hardline religious and authoritarian backbone of the Islamic Revolution, and the reformists are moderate and somewhat left-leaning.

The Iranian economy has finally industrialized, being the main industrial power of the Middle East. Oil extraction, refining and trading is the other main economic engine for Iran. However, high inflation and heavy international sections have had a negative effect for decades, alongside several case of mismanagement in state-run enterprises. Another point of relevance has been the Iranian nuclear program. In its civil side has greatly improved energy production. Nonetheless, the rumoured development of nuclear weapons has been one of the main accusations towards the Iranian government that has prompted sanctions.

Aside from that, relations with Israel and the USA are now on their lowest point, and have been tense since the Islamic revolution. However, originally both countries and Iran had great relations among them. On the American case, originally the US was seen by Iranians as a third power that could help them counter Russian (later Soviet) and British imperial ambitions, and during the Pahlavi dynasty, the US was one of Iran’s main international allies. Regarding Israel, Iran was one of the few Muslim countries to recognize Israeli statehood in 1948, as such, Israel had a great opinion of Iran and its government at the time.

The current diplomatic landscape and military operations

Israel and the USA have attacked military targets in most major cities, alongside strongholds like Kharg island (on the Persian Gulf). But they have also targeted civilian infrastructure, which has been heavily criticized internationally as civilian casualties in Iran have reached between 3 and 7 thousand dead and around 19 thousand injured (according to recent estimates from entities like the Iranian Red Crescent), alongside the destruction of several residential areas and the damage of protected heritage sites.

Iran's counterattack has been mostly centred on two types of targets: military bases that could be used to further strike against them, and more symbolical strikes against countries aligned with Israel and the USA such as Saudi Arabia.

American mobilization ("Operation Epic Fury") began in early February and consisted on several fighter jets carried by the USS Abraham Lincoln alongside missiles and drones stationed on the Middle East.

Israel mobilized fighter jets in its own soil to take part on the attacks. Israel's operation was codenamed "Operation Roaring Lion".

Iran's response (codenamed "Operation True Promise IV") mainly consisted on mass missile strikes from its territory alongside attacks with the famous Shaheed drones. Iran was supported by its proxy groups such as the Houthis in Yemen, and Hezbollah in Lebanon.

Israel's aim in the war was to orchestrate a regime change and to install Reza Pahlavi (pretender to the Iranian throne) as ruler of the country. He was the preferred option by the Israeli government as most other Iranian opposition forces are still geopolitically opposed to Israel.

The USA mainly participated to further Israeli interests on staging a regime change, although the USA has its own economic interests in the region. Several US officials, including President Trump, have stated doubts about placing Pahlavi as head of government in Iran and about his real support inside the country.

In Iran, the interests should be analysed separately, in one hand the aims of the government, and on the other of the internal opposition.

The main interest of the government of the Islamic Republic is to survive, which seems that it has achieved, as a new Supreme Leader has taken power and there have not been real protests. Alongside surviving, the Islamic Republic also has expressed clear interest in taking revenge (as shown by the raising of the Red Flag of Revenge (symbol of State anger) which it has also achieved by the most part, if we are to take their counterattacks as that revenge. Furthermore, the regime also wanted to rally more people to its side. It seems that the propagandistic actions taken by the regime, alongside a natural "rally around the flag" effect (as pointed by authors like Najmeh Bozorgmehr in the Financial

Times) caused by the conflict have indeed made more people sympathetic to the government.

On the other hand, the opposition clearly wanted a regime change, but most of them would not accept Pahlavi to rule the country. Most of the opposition is situated in the left and centre-left and the association of his figure with that of his father, who implemented a far-right police state; and with foreign imperialist powers like the US and Israel make him intolerable to most. Furthermore, most of the internal opposition in Iran shares a negative view of Israel with the ruling government, and would not accept being attacked by them.

Conclusion

The war seems to be almost over, as Trump proclaimed an American-Israeli victory on March 12th seems to be a mark of the coming end, but since the last bombing occurred in March 13th against the stronghold of Kharg island. Additionally, Israel has started a ground invasion of Lebanon against Hezbollah in March 17th, so it may seem that the war is not over. In any case, it is quite clear that any attempt at regime change has been unsuccessful, and that Iran will only entrench further and prepare for future attacks. Leaving a high possibility of an announcement of nuclear capabilities (either real or imaginary) in the near-to-mid future.

(Note as of 21/4/2026: The failure of the USA to counter the Iranian blockade of the Strait of Hormuz and the last void threats made by President Trump have caused a reopening of negotiations with Pakistan as one of the main mediators between the two parties.)

Furthermore, large unrest in the US could result in a bigger growth in opposition to Trump's administration. That could lead to the Republican party losing the following mid-term elections in November, which is nearly guaranteed to result in an impeachment against Trump.

Internationally most people have taken a hostile position towards the American-Israeli aggression without sympathising with the Iranian government. However, most Western governments and various in other regions have clearly sided with the US in the attack. This reflects a growing rift between official

statements and real public opinion that has been either widened or made more visible by the internet.

In summary, it seems that the US and Israel have not reached their goals, but Iran has also entered a very delicate position that could be exploited by a multitude of actors (Note as of 21/4/2026: The main beneficiaries at this moment are Pakistan, main mediator, and by extension its new ally of Saudi Arabia).

References

- 2026 Iran War.* (s. f.). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2026_Iran_war
- 2026 Minab school attack.* (2026). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2026_Minab_school_attack
- Masoud Pezeshkian.* (s. f.). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Masoud_Pezeshkian
- Interim Leadership Council.* (s. f.). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Interim_Leadership_Council
- Qajar Iran.* (s. f.). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qajar_Iran
- Qajar Iran. (s. f.-b). En Qajar Iran: World War I and related events.* https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qajar_Iran#World_War_I_and_related_events
- Persian Famine of 1917.* (s. f.). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Persian_famine_of_1917%E2%80%931919
- Jr Debusmann, B. (2026, 3 marzo). Trump expresses doubts over Iran's exiled crown Prince. *BBC.* <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/cm2ryq0d2mro>
- Jonko, A. J. (2026, 1 marzo). Iran Raises Red Flag Over Mosque After Khamenei Killing. What It Means. *NDTV World.* <https://www.ndtv.com/world-news/us-israel-attacks-iran-live-updates-ayatollah-ali-khamenei-israel-iran-war-news-burj-khalifa-news-dubai-attack-tehran-bombing-iran-hoists-red-flag-over-11154365>
- President Donald Trump declares victory in Iran war, vows to complete mission. (2026, 12 marzo). *THE CHOSUN Daily.*

<https://www.chosun.com/english/world-en/2026/03/12/RBRVUQWC6ZBLVORVVNK2M5W7UE/>

Iranians rethink the price of regime change. (s. f.).
<https://web.archive.org/web/20260311052130/https://www.ft.com/content/4e048ed0-9bba-4392-8cee-7f1337c0b211>

United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner. (2026, 12 marzo). *UN experts denounce aggression on Iran and Lebanon, warn of devastating regional escalation*. United Nations Human Rights Office Of The High Commissioner. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2026/03/un-experts-denounce-aggression-iran-and-lebanon-warn-devastating-regional>

Parent, D. (s. f.). 'Dark, Like Our Future': Iranians describe scenes of catastrophe after Tehran's oil depots bombed. *The Guardian*.
<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2026/mar/08/dark-like-our-future-iranians-describe-scenes-of-catastrophe-after-tehrans-oil-depots-bombed>

United States Senate. (2026). Letter to Hegseth on MiNAB bombing CIVCAS Iran. En
https://www.vanhollen.senate.gov/imo/media/doc/letter_to_hegseth_on_minab_bombing_civcas_iran.pdf.

Afkhami, A. A. (2003). Compromised constitutions: the Iranian experience with the 1918 influenza pandemic. En
https://hsrc.himmelfarb.gwu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1384&context=smhs_psych_facpubs.